

Original Research

Institutions First: The Conditional Effects of Investment Freedom on Financial Development in MENA (2004–2020)

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Abstract

This study re-examines the developmental promise of financial liberalization in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), a region characterized by institutional fragility and oil dependence. Using panel data from 11 MENA countries over the period 2004–2020, we construct a composite financial development index and estimate its determinants through fixed-effects regressions with robust Driscoll-Kraay standard errors. The results show that investment freedom significantly reduces financial development ($\beta = -0.0191$, $p < 0.000$). Importantly, the interaction between investment freedom and rule of law is also negative and significant ($\beta = -0.0067$, $p = 0.0008$), suggesting that even in countries with relatively stronger legal institutions – such as the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia – liberalization may enhance elite capture rather than broaden inclusion. In contrast, financial freedom has a positive and significant effect ($\beta = 0.0107$, $p = 0.002$). Financial globalization, whether measured by total capital flows ($\beta = 0.0347$, $p = 0.122$) or by foreign direct investment ($\beta = -0.0054$, $p = 0.488$), shows no statistically significant effect. These findings challenge the assumption that openness automatically enhances financial progress. Instead, it is acknowledged that in rentier and post-authoritarian contexts, institutional preconditions must precede liberalization. Without credible governance, financial openness risks deepening exclusion and systemic fragility rather than providing inclusive growth.

Keywords: Financial development, investment freedom, financial globalization, panel data, MENA.

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Introduction

Despite decades of reform, financial development in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) remains shallow and unequal, shaped not only by economic variables but by entrenched institutional weaknesses (Beck, 2009). Many MENA countries have implemented policies promoting investment freedom and financial globalization, expecting such liberalization to deepen financial markets and attract capital inflows. Yet the region continues to struggle with limited credit access, high financial exclusion, and underdeveloped financial institutions.

This paradox is especially pronounced in oil-rich states where financial openness often coexists with fragile institutions, suggesting that liberalization may reinforce rent-seeking and elite capture rather than drive inclusive growth (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2013; Hertog, S, 2010). While previous literature has examined the effects of economic openness on financial development globally, few studies have assessed how institutional quality and oil dependence condition these effects in the MENA context (Chinn & Ito, 2006; Tesega, 2022).

To address this gap, this study examines how investment freedom, financial globalization, and trade openness shape financial development in 11 Middle East and North African countries between 2004 and 2020, accounting for institutional heterogeneity and resource dependence. Our main question is not whether openness leads to development, but under what conditions—and for whom—it does so.

As institutional theory (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2013; North, 1990) shown, the quality of institutions determines how policies such as investment liberalization affect outcomes. In contexts of weak property rights, regulatory capture, and corruption, liberalization can foster rent-seeking and speculative behavior and undermine financial development. Therefore, the research hypotheses include:

H₁: Investment freedom negatively affects financial development in countries with poor institutional quality.

H₂: The impact of financial globalization on FD is weaker in oil-dependent economies.

Mishkin, (2009) argues that globalization can promote institutional reforms that promote financial development and economic growth. He emphasizes that opening up financial markets to foreign capital directly increases access to capital domestically and reduces its cost for those making productive investments. Furthermore, opening up domestic markets to foreign goods can promote the development of better institutions. In fact, globalization can encourage emerging economies to develop institutions that foster financial development (Mishkin, 2009).

International capital flows have increased significantly over the past three decades, especially since 1987, when most countries' capital accounts were liberalized. Transition countries, especially the European Union member states, have shown a significant inclination towards financial globalization. To this end, the effectiveness of their financial systems in capturing the benefits and mitigating the disadvantages associated with globalization becomes crucial (Tovar García, 2012).

Financial development influences saving and investment decisions, making it a crucial element in achieving higher rates of economic development and growth. Consequently, it is crucial to understand the factors that influence financial development (Ang, 2008; Levine & Zervos, 1998). Financial globalization refers to the process by which domestic financial institutions and foreign markets are integrated into the domestic financial system (Schmukler, 2004a, 2004b). Financial globalization facilitates the diffusion of optimal practices and protocols on an international scale, thereby potentially increasing corporate governance, risk diversification, foreign transaction costs, and information asymmetry (Kalemli-Ozcan et al., 2013; Tovar García, 2012). Extensive research shows that financial globalization significantly affects financial development. Given the unprecedented level of integration between countries, examining the correlation between financial globalization and financial development will be of great importance for governments and regulatory agencies. Consequently, the focal point of this paper is the aforementioned link (Tovar García, 2012). Therefore, in line with the above criteria, the main objective of the present paper is to analyze the effects of investment freedom and financial globalization on the financial progress of a specific group of countries in the Middle East and North Africa region. To achieve this goal, quantitative panel regression was used over the period 2004-2020.

This study is distinctive in that it examines the effects of investment freedom and financial freedom variables. There are not enough studies that have fully examined how investment freedom and financial globalization affect financial development in MENA countries. Hence, this study will make a valuable contribution to the empirical literature by demonstrating the relationship between financial globalization and financial development in the context of developing countries, especially the MENA region.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and presents the theoretical foundations of financial globalization and financial development and their interrelationships. Section 3 describes the economic and political characteristics of MENA member countries. Section 4 describes the research background. Section 5 presents the data and model. In Section 6, the research methodology is introduced, followed by the empirical results in this section. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper with conclusions and policy recommendations.

Literature Review

The political economy of the MENA region is deeply shaped by two structural features: institutional fragility and resource dependence. Unlike the assumptions of neoclassical economics—where liberalization leads to efficient market outcomes—the MENA context is often characterized by weak enforcement of property rights, limited checks on executive power, and entrenched patronage networks. As such, the institutional environment mediates the effects of economic policies, including those aimed at financial liberalization.

Following the institutionalist tradition (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2013; North, 1990), we argue that economic freedom—such as investment deregulation—does not operate in a vacuum. In countries with fragile institutions, liberalization may empower insider elites who exploit regulatory gaps to expand their control over financial resources. Rather than

fostering competition, this dynamic leads to financial capture, where credit flows are diverted away from productive use and toward politically connected actors.

This phenomenon is particularly salient in rentier states, where oil revenues reduce the fiscal need for taxation and accountability (El Beblawi, 2008). In such contexts, the state acts as an allocator of rents rather than a facilitator of markets—a condition (Hertog, S, 2010) terms the “allocation state.” These states often lack the institutional preconditions for financial development: independent central banks, competitive banking sectors, and transparent financial governance.

Moreover, the liberalization of capital flows in the absence of regulatory depth may attract speculative or extractive finance rather than long-term productive investment. This results in volatility, misallocation, and increased vulnerability to capital flight, particularly in oil-dependent economies with soft financial infrastructure.

In sum, MENA’s structural constraints imply that institutions, not just incentives, determine the success or failure of financial reform. Reforms that ignore political and institutional realities are likely to exacerbate inequality and entrench elite capture, rather than promote inclusive financial development.

In the literature on financial development, defining and quantifying financial development in a manner that permits cross-country comparisons is one of the fundamental issues. Due to the fact that financial development has historically been equated with financial scale and depth, its definition is predicated on the magnitude of the financial system. Nevertheless, financial development is an intricate and diverse notion. It is mandatory that the definition of financial development encompass all operations carried out by the financial system (Eryigit & Dulgeroglu, 2015).

Since the proposition of financial repression in recent decades, the notion of financial development has garnered increased attention. The literature on the correlation between financial development and economic growth has matured to a certain extent, following an approximately twenty-year period of scientific controversy. It has been established that financial development exerts a significant positive causal influence on economic growth at the macro level. The channels through which financial development affects the real sector are virtually well understood. Additionally, economic research has shifted its focus from macroeconomics to microeconomics. The International Monetary Fund contrasted the financial development indicators of nineteen Middle Eastern and North African countries in a research report. The International Monetary Fund assessed the reforms of the financial sector in the Middle East and North Africa (specifically, the countries of Sinai or Mena) as a critical requirement for these regions to attain a substantial rate of economic expansion, as stated in the report’s introduction. According to economic theories, strengthening the financial sector through the implementation of policies that reduce the costs of information, exchanges, and monitoring will increase production by boosting productivity. The assessment of the financial development index of countries in the Middle East and North Africa encompassed an examination of six sub-indices: banking sector, non-banking financial sector, legislation and supervision, monetary sector, and monetary policy formulation (Creane et al., 2006).

Due to the fact that globalization can be expanded to include social, economic, political, legal, cultural, technological, and environmental aspects, the precise definition of globalization is not agreed upon among theorists. While some theorists (Fukuyama, 2001) put forth a broad definition of globalization (Christiano et al., 1999) provided a more specific definition, attributing it to the integration that occurs in the realms of finance, environment, and economics. According to (Krugman, 1994) globalization encompasses the expansion of international capital exchanges and production relations as well as the integration of world markets.

In economics, financial globalization pertains to the intercontinental economy. The significance of financial globalization lies in the fact that it compels and encourages countries to comply with international reporting and regulatory standards. Additionally, it promotes the exchange of sophisticated technologies and knowledge from developed countries (Motelle & Biekpe, 2015).

Since the 1970s, financial globalization, or the integration of countries into the global financial system, has increased substantially, and even more so since the 1990s. It is not, however, a novel occurrence. Indeed, a substantial surge in financial globalization occurred during the classical gold standard era (1914-1880). This surge was fueled by the escalation of cross-border capital flows and the integration of both central and peripheral countries into an extensive global investment and financial network. With the outbreak of World War I, global economic expansion came to a halt and barriers hindered international financial integration between 1914 and 1945. Reconstruction was sluggish despite the fact that domestic financial markets were extensively regulated and capital flows were frequently subject to controls. The global financial system was established and operated under the Bretton Woods system from 1971 to 1945. Nevertheless, a paradigm shift in global financial integration emerged, which was characterized by the elimination of capital controls, the deregulation of domestic financial systems, and a technological revolution encompassing information and communication as well as financial product engineering. During the 1990s and beyond, this surge of financial globalization was accompanied by the rapid emergence of new markets.

The phenomenon of financial globalization has demonstrated that it presents both advantages and disadvantages for both developed and developing countries, occasionally resulting in analogous or dissimilar outcomes. On the one hand, empirical evidence and analysis have demonstrated that financial globalization can yield diverse advantages for countries. The most basic benefit is the availability of external financing at a reduced expense. Financial inclusion enhances risk diversification through the provision of a more extensive array of instruments that can be utilized to fulfill the requirements. On the other hand, similar to foreign direct investment (FDI), foreign capital can facilitate the introduction of technological advancements and knowledge that have the potential to boost domestic output (Beck et al., 2013).

It is possible that through an examination of financial globalization and the fundamental operations that a financial system must execute in order to attain a more advanced stage of financial development, private and privileged information within financial markets will initially be eradicated. The disclosure of all accessible information by the financial system (including institutions, organizations, and the market) is a

consequence of the confrontation and emerging requirements imposed by external economic factors that are not influenced by interest groups. Specifically, the involvement of international economic actors engenders competition among themselves and domestic factors, thereby facilitating the generation of more accurate and comprehensive data regarding the state of the domestic financial market. Conversely, in the event that foreign economic actors seek collaboration and collusion with domestic interest groups, the financial system is unable to furnish every accessible information to said actors. Second, the advancement of financial globalization enables the dissemination of optimal financial supervision practices and methodologies on a global scale, thereby fostering enhanced corporate governance. (Morck & Steier, 2005) note that, in contrast to the United States, the majority of capitalist countries have pyramidal organizations in which the wealthiest families own the companies; consequently, capital allocation is influenced by these interest groups and their deals with the government. However, the introduction of foreign economic factors will result in the allocation of capital by interest groups, the evaluation of companies, and the monitoring of managers, all of which will lead to an improvement in corporate governance. In contrast, (Shleifer & Vishny, 1986) contend that corporate control may be weakened as a result of liberalization, as increased liquidity diminishes the motivations of shareholders to oversee borrowers and managers. Third, risk diversification is facilitated by financial globalization. The fact that domestic economic agents and external agents can share hazards on domestic and foreign financial markets is evident on a global scale. By adopting this strategy, a nation can extend credit to international borrowers during periods of economic expansion and contraction, thereby mitigating the impact of fluctuations in income on investment and consumption (Tovar García, 2012).

Mishkin (2009) and Schmukler (2004a, b) argue that globalization has the potential to serve as a potent instrument in encouraging developing countries to enhance their institutions, thereby fostering financial advancements and economic growth. Financial globalization has the potential to facilitate financial development in developing countries in two distinct ways. One is that it can reduce the cost of capital while simultaneously increasing cash availability. Second, the facilitation of foreign financial institution access to markets enhances financial infrastructure and advances reforms within the financial sector (Mishkin, 2009; Schmukler, 2004a, 2004b).

Assets and liabilities, securities, bank loans and deposits, land ownership, and physical capital are all impacted by the globalization of financial markets. Financial transactions consist solely of the exchange of paper documents or the entry of entries into electronic ledgers. The communication revolution simplifies, accelerates, and reduces the cost of these tasks. Physical borders are not traversed by financial assets. Financial transactions are exclusively impeded by national regulations. With the relaxation of these barriers in each nation, the international financial debt of that nation has inundated domestic bond markets and inundated banking systems across the globe. These debts can serve as a conduit for savings from developed capitalist democracies to be invested in productive ventures situated in developing countries across Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Alternatively, they may induce currency crises, recessions, unemployment, and deprivation in the respective countries, or both (Tobin, 2000).

It is generally acknowledged that efficiently resourced financial markets, which are also well-regulated and developed, are a prerequisite for fostering long-term economic growth. Better developed financial systems are associated with, on average, quicker economic growth than less developed systems (King & Levine, 1993).

Mainstream economists are unequivocal regarding the prospective advantages that financial globalization may offer. According to Obstfeld (2008), “In the long-run, an open international financial system is likely to be more competitive, transparent, and efficient than a closed financial system.” Conversely, within an imperfect market environment characterized by information asymmetry, high transaction costs, and an institutional structure lacking an appropriate incentive structure, financial globalization may give rise to crises, instability, and losses. These consequences manifest themselves as abrupt adjustments (Tovar García, 2012).

Economic and Political Attributes of MENA Member States

The 2010s began amid widespread calls for political reform and economic restructuring across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), following decades of authoritarian governance. In December 2010, socioeconomic grievances and perceived institutional failures in Tunisia triggered a wave of protests that became widely known as the Arab Spring. This mobilization subsequently spread to several countries, including Egypt, Yemen, Bahrain, Libya, and Syria. A similar-scale protest movement had occurred in Iran in 2009, commonly referred to as the Green Movement. Earlier, the 2003 U.S.-led intervention in Iraq resulted in the removal of Saddam Hussein’s regime and initiated a political transition process aimed at establishing a more representative governance system.

However, the anticipated shifts toward sustained democratization and institutional consolidation did not materialize uniformly across the region. Subsequent developments, including prolonged conflicts in Syria and Libya, geopolitical tensions between Saudi Arabia and Iran, the blockade of Qatar (2017–2021), and protracted disputes over Iran’s nuclear program, highlight the persistence of political instability and governance challenges.

On the economic front, several MENA countries have engaged in regional and multilateral trade initiatives. Algeria, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Syria, and Tunisia signed bilateral free trade agreements (FTAs) with the European Union during the 1990s and 2000s, primarily focused on tariff reduction. As of the study period, 13 MENA countries were members of the World Trade Organization (WTO); Algeria, Iran, Iraq, Lebanon, Libya, Sudan, and Syria remained outside the organization (Dñabrowski & Domínguez-Jiménez, 2021).

Research Background

This section summarizes significant empirical studies examining the connection between financial globalization and financial development. The initial investigations into the correlation between financial globalization and financial development were conducted by (Levine & Zervos, 1998), (Rebeco, 1999), and (Klein & Olivei, 2008) in

close succession to the ideas put forth by (Chinn & Ito, 2002, 2006) who introduced institutional variables. According to (Bailliu, 2000), (Eichengreen & Leblang, 2003), and (Bekaert et al., 2011), the presence of a robust and regulated financial system in a nation guarantees a positive influence of financial globalization on economic development. (Read, 2004) investigated the ideas of increased regionalism and globalization, in addition to the primary determinants of economic expansion in the small nation of Iceland, in his article. In light of the findings presented in this article, further investigation is warranted concerning the impact of globalization on economic expansion. In his study, (Van Hoa, 2005) examined the impact of China's World Trade Organization membership on the country's investment and development. He did so within the broader framework of a multi-sector economy and employed a model that is grounded in the flexible and modern Keynesian approach. One of the outcomes of China's membership in the World Trade Organization, according to the findings of his research, is a rise in direct and indirect investment via an expansion of exports and imports. In his article, (Obadan, 2006) also investigated the obstacles that jeopardize the growth of the financial sector through an analysis of the financial globalization process. He argues that while financial globalization does offer intriguing advantages, it can also inflict enormous costs on society, such as the financial crisis. (Mishkin, 2009) demonstrated in his article that globalization is a crucial catalyst for institutional reforms in developing countries. Large countries can, as he suggests, assist these emerging market nations through the exchange of products and services with developing nations. In their article, (Mahutga & Smith, 2011) analyzed the impact of globalization on economic development. They examined the impact of changes in the mobility and international division of labor on fluctuations in the economic development of nations using cross-country data. According to the findings of their investigation, the countries whose average level of labor mobility was the highest had the greatest economic growth rate; thus, a high level of labor mobility causes countries to converge, whereas a low-level causes country to diverge. The relationship between financial globalization and financial development in transition countries was examined by (Tovar García, 2012) using a dynamic panel and the Blundell & Bond (1998) model. In general, the key findings indicate that financial globalization has a significant positive correlation with the growth process of the financial system, but not with the development process, that is to say, without an improved financial system performance.

(Falahaty & Law, 2012) investigated the impact of globalization on financial development. This study using the information of 9 selected member countries of the Middle East and North Africa was conducted during the time period from 1991 to 2007, and in order to examine the above relationship, the panel data technique with the autoregressive vector approach was used, and finally, based on the results, globalization has a significant positive role in promoting the financial development index has played a role.

The long-term associations among globalization, institutions, and financial development were examined by (Muye & Muye, 2017) utilizing dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS), pooled group mean (PMG), and fully modified OLS (FMOLS). (Wei, 2018) developed lessons gleaned from a recent literature review on financial globalization for the context of developing countries. (Balcilar et al., 2019) examined the relationship between financial development and globalization using panel data from 36 countries from

1996 to 2016. (Tesege, 2022) analyzed the correlation between financial globalization and financial development in 33 African countries for the period 2005 to 2019. The U-shaped relationship between financial globalization and financial development in Africa is one of the key findings of this study which states that a reduced level of financial globalization has a negative impact on financial development. (Soleimani et al., 2022) studied the nonlinear effects of globalization (composite index of globalization) on financial development (facilities granted by the banking system) in Iran during the period from 1988 to 2019 using Markov switching econometric technique. The estimation results indicate that globalization in the first regime (prosperity) has a positive effect on the financial development index, while in the second regime (recession) we see a negative relationship. (Ozturk & Nagayev, 2024) They examined the determinants of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, with a particular focus on economic growth, trade policy, financial development, and governance indicators such as effective governance and political stability. Based on the findings, this paper provides a set of policy recommendations, including promoting economic growth, increasing trade openness, improving institutional quality, diversifying the economy, and maintaining macroeconomic stability, to create a favorable environment for foreign direct investment.

Past studies showed that in most of the research conducted on the impact of financial globalization on financial development, no specific study has been conducted based on the variables of financial liberalization and investment liberalization in the Middle East and North Africa region. Therefore, in this research, the impact of financial globalization in terms of the variables of trade openness, financial liberalization and investment liberalization on financial development in selected countries of the Middle East and North Africa region has been investigated using the econometric technique of panel data. It should be noted that the use of the financial freedom index along with the investment freedom index is one of the innovations of the present research.

Data and Model

Data

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of investment freedom and financial globalization on financial development. To achieve this goal, robust panel testing was applied to panel data from 2004 to 2020 for 11 selected countries in the Middle East and North Africa region. Algeria, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, and the United Arab Emirates are the countries examined in this study. However, Iran, Iraq, Djibouti, Malta, Lebanon, Bahrain, and Yemen were excluded due to unavailability of necessary data. Table 1 provides a summary of the variables, data, and data collection method.

To capture financial development in a multidimensional manner, we constructed a composite Financial Development Index (FD_index) using three standardized indicators: credit to the private sector (% of GDP), bank branches per 100,000 adults, and the Z-score of the banking sector. These indicators reflect financial depth, access, and stability. Following the approach of (Svirydzhenka, 2016), each variable was normalized using z-

score transformation, and the final index was computed as the arithmetic mean of the three normalized values.

To examine the impact of financial globalization, two indicators of total capital inflows and outflows to GDP and financial globalization (foreign direct investment, net inflows (percentage of GDP)) were used separately.

To capture the institutional and resource-specific heterogeneity across MENA countries, we incorporated both control and interaction variables into our empirical model. The Rule of Law index was included to account for the quality of governance and institutional strength, which is widely recognized as a crucial determinant of financial development. The Oil Rents (% of GDP) variable was added as a control to reflect the resource-dependent nature of several MENA economies, where oil wealth can either facilitate or hinder financial sector growth. Furthermore, we introduced binary (dummy) variables to classify countries into high vs. low institutional quality, and oil-rich vs. non-oil economies. To test for moderating effects, we constructed interaction terms (e.g., Investment Freedom \times Institutional Quality and Financial Globalization \times Oil Rents) to examine whether the impact of liberalization policies depends on a country's institutional context or resource dependence.

This paper uses two dummy variables, one for oil-rich countries (Algeria, Libya, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Oman and Kuwait) and the other for high institutional quality (Israel, UAE, Oman, Kuwait, Jordan and Saudi Arabia). The median of the rule of law in MENA countries is 0.0928. If a country has a mean above the median, it is institutionally strong (1), otherwise it is institutionally weak (0).

Table 1. Definitions of variables and data collection procedures

Variable	Symbol	Definition and measurement method	Unit	Data source
Financial Development	FD	1. Monetary Sector credit to private sector (% GDP) 2. Bank Z-score 3. Bank branches per 100,000 adults	Unitless	Calculated
Financial Globalization	FG & FDI	Total input and output of capital to GDP & Financial_Globalization (Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP))	Unitless	World bank
Investment_Freedom	IF	Index of investment Freedom of Heritage Foundation	Scaled at 0-to-100	Heritage Foundation data base

Variable	Symbol	Definition and measurement method	Unit	Data source
Financial_Freedom	FF	Index of financial liberalization of Heritage Foundation	Scaled at 0-to-100	Heritage Foundation data base
Trade Openness	TO	Imports plus exports to GDP ratio	Unitless	World bank
Institutional variable	Rule of Law	Rule of Law	Scaled at -2/5-to +2/5	World bank WGI
Control variable	Oil Rents	Oil rents (% of GDP)	Unitless	World bank WDI
Interactive variable	IFL	If*Rule of Law	Unitless	Calculated
Interactive variable	FGO	FG*Oil rents (% of GDP)	Unitless	Calculated
Oil dummy	Oil_Rich	(Algeria, Libya, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Oman and Kuwait) =1 The rest of the countries are equal to zero.	Unitless	Manually
Institutional dummy	High_inst_Quality	(Israe=0/94, UAE=0/56, Oman=0/46, Kuwait=0/35, Jordan=0/29 and Saudi Arabia=0.0928) =1. The rest of the countries are equal to zero.	Unitless	Manually

The present study used a two-factor measure, a quantitative measure of financial flows, to assess the extent of financial globalization. This measure represents the ratio of gross capital flows to GDP or the sum of capital inflows and outflows. The reason for using this measure is to consider bilateral flows and assess financial globalization in a more rational and consistent manner (Kose et al., 2010). Foreign direct investment is also used to strengthen the test for assessing financial globalization. Financial development is approximated by the ratio of monetary to private sector credit to GDP captures the size of financial intermediation. In addition to two proxies of sustainability (Bank Z-score) and access (Bank branches per 100,000 adults). This measure Credit to private sector (% of GDP) has been used in a number of empirical studies, such as (Badeeb & Lean, 2017; Jung, 2017; Musamali & Eliud Moyi, 2014; Ololade, 2014; Ono, 2017), and (Idries Mohammed Al-Jarrah et al., n.d.). Using the usual method, trade openness, the explanatory variable, was calculated as the ratio of imports to exports to GDP. Tariff rates were ignored due to incomplete data availability. The Heritage Foundation's Economic Freedom Index, which ranges from 0 to 100, was used to quantify countries' investment and financial independence during the study periods. These indices were also not available from the Fraser Institute for robustness testing, and only the Economic Freedom Index was available.

In this study, we utilized two distinct proxies for financial globalization: net inflows of foreign direct investment (FDI) as a narrow measure, and the sum of capital inflows and outflows as a broader measure. While both variables capture different aspects of financial openness, the interaction term was constructed only for the FDI variable. This is because FDI is typically more responsive to long-term structural factors such as oil dependency and institutional quality, whereas portfolio flows and short-term capital movements tend to be more volatile and opportunistic in nature. Hence, the FDI × Oil Rents interaction allows us to test the theoretical claim that resource-dependent economies may attract FDI that does not necessarily contribute to financial sector development. Including interaction terms for both measures would also increase multicollinearity risk without substantial theoretical benefit.

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics of the study variables, including the mean, standard deviation, as well as the minimum and maximum values of the data.

Table 2. Statistical summary of research variables

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
FD	184	0.027998	0.570089	-1.08252	1.456226
FG (TIO)	184	25.96276	8.085607	8.442421	51.77961
FG (FDI)	184	2.917828	3.001389	-2.76001	23.53729
FF	184	46.63043	15.59579	10.0000	70.00000
TO	184	25.95180	8.096940	8.442421	51.77961
IF	184	49.34783	18.82066	5.000000	85.00000
Oil rents	184	18.36473	18.98247	0.000212	64.81644
Rule of Law	184	0.024101	0.613421	-1.69788	1.130978
if*Rule of Law	184	7.928467	29.21750	-43.1401	90.47828
FG*Oil rents	184	35.73720	58.37130	-52.0761	413.0473

Model Introduction

The model used in this research is based on the following model that links the two parameters of financial development and financial globalization (Tesega, 2022).

$$fd_{it} = a_{it} + b_1fg(tio)_{it} + b_2fg(fdi)_{it} + b_2to_{it} + b_3if_{it} + b_4ff_{it} + b_5Rule\ of\ Law_{it} + b_6Oil\ rents_{it} + b_7If * Rule\ of\ Law_{it} + b_8FG * Oil\ rents_{it} + b_9Oil_Rich_{it} + b_{10}High_inst_Quality_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Here fd_{it} is financial development of country i at time t ; fg_{it} is financial globalization of country i at time t ; to_{it} is trade openness of country i at time t ; if_{it} is investment freedom of country i at time t ; and ff_{it} is the financial freedom of country i at time t . b_1 and b_{10} represent the coefficients of explanatory variables and a_{it} is the constant term.

Research Methodology

In this study, the impact of investment freedom and financial globalization on financial development in 11 MENA countries during the period 2004–2020 is examined using a

Panel Data model. The Robust Estimation method is employed to mitigate issues arising from heteroskedasticity and cross-sectional dependence.

Panel data, due to its combination of cross-sectional (countries) and time-series (years) dimensions, offers greater advantages compared to conventional cross-sectional or time-series models. These advantages include better control over heteroskedasticity and a reduction in estimation biases (Baltagi, 2021)

Pre-estimation tests

- Stationarity test: The Dickey-Fuller (ADF) stationarity test was used to check stationarity. The results showed that all variables except *if*Rule of Law*, *Financial_Freedom*, *Bank branches per 100,000 adults*, *Rule of Law* are at the stationary level.
- Autocorrelation test: The Durbin-Watson test was used to check autocorrelation in the residuals of the model. The results showed that there is significant autocorrelation.
- Heterogeneity of variance test: The LR test was used to check the existence of heterogeneity of variance, which showed that there is heterogeneity of variance in the model.
- The Granger Causality test was used to check the endogenous relationships between pairs of variables, and endogeneity relationships between variables were observed.
- Multiple collinearity test: To check the existence of collinearity between independent variables, the variance inflation coefficient was calculated. The results showed that there is no strong collinearity between the variables of the model.
- Cross-sectional correlation test: Cross-sectional correlation means that economic shocks in one country may affect other countries as well. The Pesaran CD Test was used to examine cross-sectional correlation. The results confirmed the existence of cross-sectional correlation.
- Selection of the appropriate model (. Likelihood Ratio and Hausman test): The Likelihood Ratio and Hausman test were used to select between the fixed effects model and the random effects model. The test results showed that the fixed effects model was more appropriate. Therefore, in this study, the fixed effects model was used along with robust estimation.
- Model estimation with robust methods: Due to problems such as variance heterogeneity and cross-sectional correlation, robust methods were used to estimate the model.
- The Panel Regression Results test was used to examine the U-curve. The results led to the rejection of the nonlinearity of this curve.

Table 3. Unit root test

Method	Variable	ADF Statistic	p-value
Dickey-Fuller (ADF)	Monetary Sector credit to private sector	-3.2422	0.0177
	Bank Z-score	-35527	0.0067
	Bank branches per 100,000 adults	-2.1397	0.2289
	FD index	-3.1945	0.0203
	Oil rents (% of GDP)	-2.8913	0.0464
	Rule of Law	-2.4438	0.1298
	Investment Freedom	-3.6147	0.0055
	Financial Freedom	-2.3572	0.1542
	Financial Globalization (FDI)	-3.7165	0.0039
	Trade Openness	-3.7359	0.0036
	Financial_Globalization (Foreign direct investment, net inflows)	-4.2376	0.0006
	if*Rule of Law	-2.7119	0.0720
FG (FDI)*Oil rents (% of GDP)	-5.4105	0.0000	

Several key variables in our model, including Bank Branches per 100,000 adults, Rule of Law, and Financial Freedom, were found to be non-stationary at level based on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. However, instead of differencing the data, we further conducted the Kao (1999) cointegration test, which strongly rejected the null hypothesis of no cointegration. This suggests the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. In such cases, the literature supports the use of variables in levels when estimating long-run panel models, especially under a fixed-effects specification. Furthermore, the Dickey-Fuller tests applied confirmed stationarity in some variables and long-run properties in others. Therefore, we retained the level form to preserve economic interpretability and avoid losing long-term information, as differencing would eliminate essential structural insights.

Table 4. Kao Residual Cointegration Test

ADF	t-Statistic	Prob.
	-2.595486	0.0047
Residual variance	0.030472	
HAC variance	0.033372	

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test (Durbin-Watson)

	Durbin-Watson Statistic
Autocorrelation Test (Durbin-Watson)	0.272021
	*Note: significant autocorrelation detected.

According to the value obtained from the Durbin-Watson test statistic, which indicates that the closer the value is to 2, the null hypothesis of autocorrelation is rejected. Therefore, in this case, there is autocorrelation.

Table 6. Heteroskedasticity LR Test

	Value	df	Probability
Heteroskedasticity LR Test	208.4059	11	0.0000

*Note: Heteroskedasticity detected. Use robust standard errors.

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test (VIF)

Feature	VIF
Const	40.746979
Financial Freedom	4.239034
Investment Freedom	3.805852
Financial Globalization	1.003934
Trade Openness	1.394400
Financial Globalization (Foreign direct investment, net inflows	2.056150
Rule of Law	6.333612
Oil rents (% of GDP)	4.957966
Trade Openness	1.704522
High inst Quality	7.357692
Oil Rich	7.147963
if*Rule of Law	4.418703
FG*Oil rents (% of GDP)	2.356823

Notes: Interpretation of VIF values:

- *VIF < 5* → Multicollinearity is acceptable, and there is no serious issue.
- *VIF between 5 and 10* → Moderate multicollinearity exists, which may cause problems.
- *VIF > 10* → Severe multicollinearity is present and should be addressed (e.g., by removing one of the correlated variables).

1 If only the VIF value for the constant term is high, it is usually not a problem and can be ignored.

2 If other independent variables also have high VIF values, there is a strong possibility of multicollinearity, and it should be investigated.

The presence of multicollinearity was examined using the variance inflation factor (VIF). While some variables, such as rule of law and institutional/oil dummy variables, showed VIF values slightly above 5, this was to be expected given the inclusion of interaction terms and constructs with conceptual overlap. Since the estimated coefficients remained stable and interpretable, and since these variables are theoretically important, we retained them in the model. Overall, multicollinearity does not appear to significantly affect the results.

Table 8. Cross-sectional Dependence

Method	CD Statistic	p-value
Pesaran CD Test	2.8887	0.0077

The (Pesaran, 2004) CD test confirmed statistically significant cross-sectional dependence among countries (CD = 2.8887, p = 0.0077), indicating that common shocks or spillover effects may influence multiple countries simultaneously. Therefore, robust standard errors were used to ensure valid inference.

Table 9. Likelihood Ratio (LR)

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	54.250193	(10,164)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	268.724549	10	0.0000

Table 10. Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	4.268480	9	0.8929

To determine whether fixed effects are necessary in the model, a redundant fixed effects test (F-statistic = 54.25, p = 0.0000; Chi-square = 268.72, p = 0.0000) was conducted. The results indicate that cross-sectional fixed effects are statistically significant, suggesting that unobserved heterogeneity across units is present and should be accounted for by using the fixed effects model. In addition, the Hausman specification test suggested that random effects might be appropriate (p = 0.89), but given the strong evidence of fixed effects from the LR test, the fixed effects model with robust standard errors is preferred.

A pairwise Granger causality test was conducted to examine the potential endogeneity and directional relationships among the variables. The results indicate significant unidirectional causalities from ifl and Rule of law to fdi; from ifl and Rule of law to FGO; from financial_globalization to oil rents and Trade_Openness; and from Financial_Freedom to Investment_Freedom. Bidirectional causality was found between financial_globalization and Trade_Openness. These findings suggest that certain financial openness indicators exhibit predictive power over others, highlighting the need for robust estimation methods to address potential simultaneity bias in the econometric model.

Table 11. Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

From \ To	FD_index	FDI	FGO	FIN_F	FIN_G	IFL	INV_F	Rule of LAW	OIL rents	TRD_OPN
FD_index	-	0.2708	0.6683	0.3274	0.1853	0.8949	0.4308	0.5218	0.462	0.2302
FDI	0.0911	-	0.0628	0.3743	0.0682	0.0003*	0.2547	0.0035*	0.1276	0.0717
FGO	0.3465	0.2589	-	0.141	0.0697	0.0287*	0.067	0.0329*	0.0528	0.0855

From \ To	FD_index	FDI	FGO	FIN_F	FIN_G	IFL	INV_F	Rule of LAW	OIL rents	TRD_OPN
FIN_F	0.0612	0.4437	0.4744	-	0.3712	0.9212	0.0393*	0.7647	0.3313	0.4062
FIN_G	0.0784	0.9571	0.3218	0.2961	-	0.3981	0.2752	0.8311	0.0452*	0.0026**
IFL	0.382	0.6837	0.5703	0.9212	0.7646	-	0.088	0.1151	0.9365	0.17
INV_F	0.7646	0.5495	0.2015	0.4819	0.001*	0.6855	-	0.9171	0.5937	0.4616
Rule of LAW	0.2296	0.4509	0.067	0.7647	0.3177	0.782	0.8164	-	0.5991	0.267
OIL rents	0.5036	0.1576	0.0772	0.3313	0.304	0.9365	0.6761	0.7334	-	0.3987
TRD_OPN	0.0569	0.9822	0.3577	0.4062	0.7033	0.9	0.4616	0.267	0.3987	-

Note *: Significant at the 10% level

** : Significant at the 5% level

Figure 1. Granger causality network

To account for variance heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and potential cross-sectional dependence in an unbalanced panel data set, the covariance estimator of (Driscoll & Kraay, 1998) is used. This approach allows for consistent inference by adjusting the standard errors to handle general forms of serial correlation and spatial dependence across countries. This estimation uses a Bartlett kernel with bandwidth 2 to estimate the long-run covariance matrix. This method is particularly suitable for the analysis of the present study given the presence of time series changes in a panel structure and the possibility of common shocks affecting multiple countries simultaneously.

Table 12. Panel OLS Estimation Summary

Statistic	Value
Dependent Variable	FD_index
Estimator	PanelOLS
Covariance Estimator	Driscoll-Kraay (Kernel: Bartlett, Bandwidth: 2)
Number of Observations	184
Number of Entities	11
Time Periods	2004–2020

Statistic	Value
R-squared (Overall)	0.6046
R-squared (Between)	0.7518
R-squared (Within)	-0.4686
Log-Likelihood	-71.81
F-statistic (Model)	23.913
P-value (F-statistic)	0.0000
Distribution	F (11, 172)
Robust F-statistic	582.33
Robust P-value	0.0000
Bandwidth	2
Kernel	Bartlett

The results of the fixed effects panel model with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors confirm the statistical robustness of the core specification. The robust F-statistic ($F = 582.33$, $p < 0.001$) strongly rejects the null hypothesis of joint insignificance, indicating that the overall model is highly significant.

The results of the panel regression using Driscoll–Kraay (1998) robust standard errors indicate that investment freedom has a negative and statistically significant effect on financial development ($\beta = -0.0191$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that greater openness to capital inflows, in the absence of strong institutional safeguards, may foster rent-seeking or financial capture rather than productive intermediation. In contrast, financial freedom exhibits a positive and significant association with financial development ($\beta = 0.0107$, $p = 0.002$), highlighting the role of domestic financial sector deregulation in fostering market depth and access.

Countries classified as having high institutional quality show substantially higher levels of financial development ($\beta = 1.3269$, $p < 0.001$), whereas oil-rich economies exhibit significantly lower financial development ($\beta = -1.245$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the resource curse hypothesis.

Notably, the interaction term between investment freedom and the rule of law is negative and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.0067$, $p = 0.0008$). This finding indicates that even in countries with relatively stronger legal institutions—such as the UAE, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia—the expansion of investment freedom may reinforce elite-driven financial structures rather than broaden inclusion. This pattern aligns with the political economy of semi-authoritarian rentier states, where formal institutions are often co-opted to legitimize preferential access to capital for politically connected actors (Hertog, S, 2010). Taken together, these results underscore that the sequencing of reforms matters: financial openness, particularly in investment regimes, is unlikely to yield development dividends without prior institutional transformation that ensures accountability, transparency, and contestability.

Table 13. Driscoll-Kraay

Constant (Intercept)	0.1013	0.1059	0.9571	0.3399	-0.1076	0.3103
Investment Freedom	-0.0191	0.0031	-6.2499	0.0000	-0.0251	-0.013
Financial Freedom	0.0107	0.0035	3.1096	0.0022	0.0039	0.0176
Financial Globalization (Total Capital Inflows & Outflows / GDP)	0.0347	0.0223	1.5537	0.1221	-0.0094	0.0787
FDI (Foreign Direct Investment / GDP)	-0.0054	0.0078	-0.6951	0.4879	-0.0209	0.01
Rule of Law	-0.2169	0.1918	-1.1307	0.2598	-0.5955	0.1617
Oil rents (% of GDP)	0.0043	0.0036	1.2217	0.2235	-0.0027	0.0114
Trade Openness	-0.0224	0.0227	-0.9902	0.3235	-0.0672	0.0223
High inst Quality (Dummy: 1 if high institutional quality)	1.3269	0.0975	13.612	0.0000	1.1345	1.5193
Oil Rich (Dummy: 1 if oil-rich economy)	-1.245	0.109	-11.427	0.0000	-1.4601	-1.03
Interaction: if*Rule of Law	-0.0067	0.002	-3.4025	0.0008	-0.0105	-0.0028
Interaction: FG*Oil rents (% of GDP)	-0.0006	0.0005	-1.1191	0.2647	-0.0016	0.0005

Discussion and Conclusion

The estimation results based on the Driscoll–Kraay (1998) robust standard errors offer nuanced insights into the political economy of financial development in the Middle East and North Africa. First, investment freedom exerts a statistically significant negative effect on financial development ($\beta = -0.0191$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that liberalizing capital inflows without commensurate institutional safeguards may exacerbate rent-seeking and financial capture rather than foster productive intermediation.

Notably, the interaction term between investment freedom and the rule of law is also negative and significant ($\beta = -0.0067$, $p = 0.0008$). This finding indicates that even in countries with relatively stronger legal institutions—such as the UAE, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia—the expansion of investment freedom intensifies distortions in financial allocation. In these semi-authoritarian rentier states, formal institutions often serve to legitimize preferential access for politically connected elites, turning liberalization into a channel for elite consolidation rather than inclusion. This interpretation aligns with the political economy literature on “institutionalized rentierism” in MENA (Hertog, S, 2010) and refines Hypothesis 1: it is not merely weak institutions that undermine liberalization, but the nature of institutional strength—when formal rules coexist with closed political orders, openness may deepen fragility.

In contrast, financial freedom shows a positive and significant association with financial development ($\beta = 0.0107$, $p = 0.002$), underscoring the importance of domestic financial sector reforms—such as interest rate liberalization and banking competition—in fostering market depth and access.

The dummy variables further confirm structural divides: countries with high institutional quality exhibit substantially higher financial development ($\beta = 1.3269$, $p < 0.001$), while oil-rich economies lag significantly ($\beta = -1.245$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the resource curse hypothesis.

Regarding financial globalization, neither total capital flows ($\beta = 0.0347$, $p = 0.122$) nor FDI ($\beta = -0.0054$, $p = 0.488$) shows a statistically significant effect. Moreover, the interaction between financial globalization and oil rents is insignificant ($\beta = -0.0006$, $p = 0.265$), leading us to reject Hypothesis 2. This suggests that oil dependence does not systematically condition the impact of openness—likely because capital flows in these economies are dominated by state channels that bypass domestic financial intermediaries altogether.

In sum, the findings confirm that institutions—not markets—determine the developmental payoff of liberalization. In rentier and post-authoritarian settings, openness without accountability risks entrenching elite capture rather than expanding financial inclusion.

Policy recommendations

Short-term (1-2 years): It is recommended to first establish institutional preconditions. Avoid liberalizing investment policies in weak institutional environments. Instead,

strengthen enforcement, independent regulators, and anti-corruption investment frameworks, and publish governance audits of financial reforms before implementation.

Medium-term (3-5 years): Prioritize banking liberalization in prioritizing domestic financial sector reforms—particularly lowering interest rate caps, improving banking transparency, and digital access.

Introduce incentive schemes for capital inflows only where clear institutional safeguards are in place.

Long-term (5+ years): Globalization readiness: Design a long-term roadmap for financial globalization, focusing on absorptive capacity (e.g., capital markets, fintech regulation). Create regional platforms to harmonize financial standards in MENA countries with similar oil and institutional profiles.

"Liberalization without institution-building is not development — it's deregulated fragility."

This study reaffirms that MENA's future financial resilience depends not on how open it becomes, but how well-prepared its institutions are to manage openness. Without credible governance, even good policies can backfire.

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